

BLOOM'S TAXONOMY AND SCAFFOLDING IN THE FORMATION OF FOREIGN LANGUAGE COMMUNICATIVE COMPETENCE

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Annotation: This article discusses current issues related to the organization of an effective process of teaching a foreign language in grades 8-9 in secondary schools. Along with this, a system of some tasks is provided using Bloom's taxonomy and the Scaffolding strategy, which influence the development of critical thinking, which contributes to the formation of foreign language communicative competence of school students.

Key words: foreign language communicative competence, tasks, educational process, school, critical thinking.

Annotatsiya: Ushbu maqolada umumta'lim maktablarining 8-9-sinflarida chet tilini o'qitishning samarali jarayonini tashkil etishning dolzarb masalalari muhokama qilinadi. Shu bilan birga, maktab o'quvchilarining chet tilidagi kommunikativ kompetentsiyasini shakllantirishga yordam beradigan tanqidiy fikrlashni rivojlantirishga ta'sir qiluvchi Bloom taksonomiyasi va "Iskala" strategiyasidan foydalangan holda ba'zi vazifalar tizimi taqdim etiladi.

Kalit so'zlar: chet tilining kommunikativ kompetensiyasi, vazifalar, o'quv jarayoni, maktab, tanqidiy fikrlash.

Аннотация: В данной статье рассматриваются актуальные вопросы, связанные с организацией эффективного процесса обучения иностранному языку в 8-9 классах средних образовательных школах. Наряду с этим приводится система некоторых заданий с использованием таксономии Блума и стратегии Скаффолдинга, которые влияют на развитие критического мышления, способствующее формированию иноязычной коммуникативной компетенции учащихся школ.

Ключевые слова: иноязычная коммуникативная компетенция, задания, учебный процесс, школа, критическое мышление.

In the modern world, due to the emergence of many methodological studies that touch on many issues of foreign language effective teaching, the teachers are faced with difficulties in choosing and applying the most optimal among them, motivating, and developing communicative competence of the secondary schools' students. The main strategic direction of an effective process of teaching a foreign language is the preparation of students who will be in demand as specialists of a new format, that is, with knowledge of a foreign

language, with critical and creative thinking. Thus, every 21st century educator recognizes that effective learning lies in providing active practice in speaking and writing as well as opportunities for reflection, analysis and critical thinking.

After years of observation in secondary schools, it has become evident that there is a discrepancy between the rigorous standards for foreign language communicative competence and the inadequate proficiency of students in speaking foreign languages. Therefore, it is crucial to seek out viable approaches to create an efficient learning environment that encourages the cultivation of critical thinking skills, which are essential components in fostering foreign language communicative competence in students[5].

For the purposes of this paper, foreign language communicative competence is defined as an individual's aptitude, gained through a well-structured educational program aimed at teaching a foreign language, to proficiently utilize common turns of phrase from foreign language speech patterns in a range of both predictable and impromptu conversational contexts. Through this ability, students are able to demonstrate their capacity for critical thinking as they work towards achieving their communicative objectives in the foreign language.

Critical thinking, as defined by Watson and Glaser (1980), is a complex combination of attitudes, knowledge and skills that includes the following aspects[2]:

- a) Curiosity and the ability to identify problems and have the ability to find evidence to support the truth of statements;
- b) Understanding the conditions necessary to draw correct conclusions;
- c) The ability to generate ideas and generalizations supported by logical arguments;
- d) The ability to apply these relationships and knowledge in practice.

According to Mohd Nazir Bin Md Zabit (2018), critical thinking is the kind of thinking that involves making reasoned judgments that are logical and well thought out, where the student does not simply accept all the arguments and conclusions that he encounters, but takes a position that involves doubting such arguments and conclusions. In addition, such thinking requires the student to strive to see what evidence is used to support a particular argument or conclusion [3].

B. Bloom's Taxonomy and Scaffolding are the effective methods for introducing critical thinking technology which leads to developing

communicative competence of students namely of 8-9 grades. Bloom's Taxonomy provides opportunities for students to progress through different levels of learning, from acquiring basic knowledge and skills to the ability to think creatively and solve complex problems within a given lesson topic. Therefore, when developing curricula and teaching classes, teachers need to learn to integrate all levels of this structure in order to create an effective educational process and achieve high-quality results[4].

Combining Bloom's Taxonomy and the scaffolding method in lesson planning can help teachers create effective and engaging lessons that cater to the different levels and needs of their students. Here are some examples of how these two methods can be combined:

Bloom's Taxonomy

- Determine the level of thinking skills required for each task:** Using Bloom's Taxonomy, teachers can identify the level of thinking skills required for each task and create tasks that correspond to the level of each group. For example, for a beginner level, teachers can create tasks that focus on understanding basic phrases and words, while for an advanced level, tasks can focus on analyzing complex texts or creating original texts in a foreign language.
- Create tasks that gradually increase in complexity:** Using the scaffolding method, teachers can create tasks that gradually increase in complexity, allowing students to build on their existing knowledge and skills. For example, for a beginner level, teachers can start with simple tasks such as filling in the blanks in sentences with the correct words, and gradually move on to more complex tasks such as writing short stories on a given topic.
- Provide support and hints:** Teachers can provide support and hints in tasks that will help students complete them. For example, for beginner levels, teachers

can provide a dictionary with translations or sentence structure, and reduce this support as they progress to higher levels.

4. **Use feedback and evaluation:** Teachers can create evaluation criteria for each level and task so that students know what is expected of them. Providing feedback that helps them improve their skills is also important.

5. **Use a variety of tasks:** Teachers can create diverse tasks to stimulate different aspects of language learning, such as reading, writing, speaking, and listening comprehension. This will allow students to diversify their experience.

6. **Adapt to individual needs:** Teachers can take into account individual needs and interests of students. Some may be more motivated to learn certain topics or use certain sources (such as movies or music) to learn the language.

7. **Consider cultural context:** If language learning is related to a specific culture, teachers can include tasks that will help students understand this cultural context.

By combining Bloom's Taxonomy and the scaffolding method, teachers can create a comprehensive and effective lesson plan that caters to the different levels and needs of their students. This approach allows students to gradually deepen their skills and progress in language learning, making the process more systematic and efficient.

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